

Table 2. Changes in Mn, Fe, soil pH, and ESP in submerged sodic soil as affected by amendments during the growth period of rice crop (av of 4 replications).

Amendment	Duration of submergence prior to planting (d)	Extractable Mn ^a				Extractable Fe				Soil pH after crop harvest	ESP
		A (ppm)	B (ppm)	C (ppm)	D (ppm)	A (ppm)	B (ppm)	C (ppm)	D (ppm)		
None (control)	0	2.2	11.9	11.8	10.5	3.0	14.5	14.5	14.0	10.3	82.8
	30	12.5	11.6	11.5	10.8	12.9	15.6	16.0	15.5	10.1	81.0
Gypsum	0	2.5	14.0	15.5	15.0	2.7	16.8	22.0	18.0	9.5	37.5
	30	15.0	16.5	16.8	15.8	15.5	20.6	25.5	22.6	9.3	35.2
Pyrite	0	2.0	17.5	18.0	17.5	3.5	31.5	32.6	30.8	9.6	39.6
	30	17.8	18.5	18.5	18.0	32.8	33.0	32.6	31.6	9.4	37.5
Farmyard manure	0	2.6	62.8	70.0	68.8	3.4	60.5	64.0	60.5	9.9	72.5
	30	65.7	68.6	78.5	70.5	59.8	65.8	65.5	62.0	9.8	62.0
Rice husk	0	2.4	40.5	48.0	45.5	3.5	44.5	45.3	40.6	10.0	74.5
	30	48.5	50.6	54.6	50.1	45.6	48.5	48.0	45.3	9.9	70.1

^aA = at the time of transplanting, B = 30 days after transplanting, C = 60 days after transplanting, D = 90 days after transplanting.

and gypsum requirement 25 t/ha at Gudha experimental farm of CSSRI, Karnal.

Amendments were added at flooding except for pyrite, which was applied 3 days before flooding under moist conditions to ensure proper oxidation. Soil was submerged until Jaya was transplanted in standing water 18 Jul 1982, and maintained thus throughout the crop period. Urea at 150 kg N/ha and 40 kg ZnSO₄/ha were applied to the crop. One-half the N

and all the Zn were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 weeks of crop growth. The crop was harvested 30 Oct 1982.

The effect on grain yield of 30 d pre-submergence was significant for farmyard manure and rice husk where there had not been previous flooding (Table 1). Gypsum and pyrite reduced pH and ESP more (Table 2) and produced higher

yields than other treatments at 0 days submergence, but farmyard manure produced equal yields at 30 d pre-submergence.

Extractable Fe and Mn increased with duration of submergence in the following order: farmyard manure, rice husk, pyrite, and gypsum (Table 2). The effect of pre-submergence was conspicuous up to 60 d of crop growth but remained constant or declined slightly beyond 60 d. □

Effect of USG placement and planting geometry on yield of random-planted rice

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We evaluated the feasibility of urea supergranule (USG) deep placement in randomly transplanted rice, a planting practice followed by most Indian farmers. We also compared deep placement at 24.5- × 24.5-cm and 20- × 20-cm spacing as an economy measure, and broadcast application of USG vs prilled urea. Treatments were in a randomized block design with three replications.

In random transplanting, deep placement increased Jaya yield by 0.4 t/ha and Govind yield by 1.1 t/ha (Table 1) over yields with broadcast fertilizer. Yield for 6-7 seedlings/hill spaced at 24.5 × 24.5 cm equaled that of 4 seedlings/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The wider spacing could reduce hand point placement cost by 15% (labor). USG yields were signif-

Table 1. Deep placement vs broadcast application of USG at 60 kg N/ha under different planting geometries during 1982 rainy season at Pantnagar, India.

Planting geometry	Seedlings per hill ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Broadcast ^b	Placement
<i>Jaya (medium duration)</i>			
Random (farmers' practice)	6-7	5.0	5.4
Row 24.5 × 24.5 cm	6-7	4.2	5.6
Row 20 × 20 cm recommended practice	4 ^c	4.1	4.9
<i>Govind (short duration)</i>			
Random - farmers' practice	6-7	3.5	4.6
Row 24.5 × 24.5 cm	6-7	3.7	4.3
Row 20 × 20 cm, recommended practice	4 ^c	4.3	4.5
Mean		4.1	4.9
LSD 5% broadcast vs placement			0.4
CV (%)			12

^aTo give 100 seedlings/m². ^bUSG was dissolved and mixed because of light rains following application, however, it was not incorporated. ^cThe seedling number was increased from 2 (normal) to 4/hill due to late planting (30 Jul). Late plantings are common with poor farmers.

Table 2. Broadcast and incorporation of USG vs prilled urea at 60 kg N/ha in very late planting during 1982 rainy season at Pantnagar, India.

N fertilizer	Grain yield (t/ha)
Urea supergranule	2.1
Urea	1.5
LSD 5%	0.5
CV	8%

icantly superior to those with prilled urea for broadcast and incorporation application (Table 2); however, yield was only 2 t/ha because the crop was late. □